

Proposal of Method for Risk Assessment of Project-Based Learning Failure via AHP and BBN – A Case Study

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Abstract

Project-based learning has been used in engineering education because it is expected to develop students' professional knowledge. Project-based learning research and practices in engineering education are growing. The author conducted in-depth literature research to identify the risk factors in PBL application and observed that risk assessment in implementing the PBL via Analytical Hierarchy Process and Bayesian Belief Networks had not been addressed. The study aims to propose a method to identify the risks of using the Project-Based Learning method and involving companies when teaching engineering disciplines to engineering students. A Case Study was conducted on the application of PBL to support local companies in a specific region. The risks were identified, a relationship digraph was used to identify the categories of risks, a survey was conducted to elicit risk probabilities, AHP was used to estimate risk impact, the global risk scores were estimated, and the responses to the risks were defined. BBN was also used to combine the probabilities of risks and perform sensitivity analysis. Future research directions for engineering education researchers are proposed to optimize Project-based learning curriculum design. The study provides a method to be used by professors, students, and decision-makers to identify risk factors that can impact the quality of teaching in engineering education and implement proper risk responses to the risks. The contribution is significant since it improves the quality of universities.

Keywords: Active Learning; Engineering Education; PBL; Risk Assessment, BBN, AHP

1 Introduction

Student-centered teaching methods by using Project-based learning (PBL) have been widely used. Still, universities find it difficult to deal with unexpected issues during the implementation phase and often return to traditional teaching methods (Henderson, 2012). Therefore, it is essential to identify, describe, and deal with risk factors that directly impact PBLs. It has been noticed that current literature on the Use of PBL in engineering education has not addressed the risks of PBL failure, and even less attention has been paid to risk responses to ensure excellence in projects. In this study, the author conducted a literature review to identify and list key risk factors when implementing PBL in engineering education. Being aware of these risks and how to respond to them can improve the chances of success when implementing PBL to enhance student learning and provide a sustainable teaching method at universities. The objective is to propose a method for risk assessment using Analytical Hierarchy Process (AHP) and Bayesian Belief Networks (BBN) to identify the risks and responses to ensure successful PBLs are conducted in collaboration with local companies. If risk factors are not identified, and proper responses are not provided PBL project can fail. This study assesses the risks and completes a gap in the literature by assessing the risk factors of using the Project-Based Learning Method in teaching engineering students. The diversity of risk factors presented here highlights the complexity of implementing PBL in engineering education. To be addressed, most of these risks require proper responses, and this need justifies this project. If risks are not identified and appropriately addressed, PBL projects can fail, and the students, professors, and partner organizations will not obtain the expected benefits. This paper is significant since it will help the development of skills and practice of professors and students and increase the quality of PBL. It is noteworthy here that the study focuses on project-based learning involving companies. Successful PBLs, in this case, will result in a significant reduction of business risks and achievement of excellence in quality and organizational safety. None of the studies present herein dealt with risk assessment and its impacts on PBL. The literature revealed that most previous studies addressed PBL and challenges without giving a methodology for risk prioritization using AHP (Analytical Hierarchy Process) and Bayesian Belief Networks.

The paper responds to the following research questions:

Research Question 1: What are the most significant risk factors for using PBL in collaboration with local companies when teaching engineering students?

Research Question 2: What are the probability and the impact of these risks and the global risk scores?

Research Question 3: What are the responses to high RPN risks, and how to combine the risks and conduct a sensitivity analysis?

This paper is divided into five sections; the first introduces the concepts of the study, the second describes PBL, the challenges and Risk Assessment of PBL Failure, BBN (Bayesian Belief Network), AHP (Analytical Hierarchy Process), and Section 3 describes the Methodology, section 4 results, and section 5 concludes.

2 Project-Based Learning

Previous significant studies about PBL Methodology and Challenges in its implementation are presented in subsections 2.1 and 2. 2.

2.1 Design of PBL Method

Previous significant studies about PBL are presented herein. Moliner et al. (2019) developed a work focused on describing the experience of using PBL methodology in Materials Science courses conducted by four different Spanish universities on different engineering degrees. The author analyzed and evaluated how the PBL was perceived by the students and lecturers who participated in the PBL process. Setiawan (2019) conducted a study focusing on the implementation of PBL, specifically on the opportunities and challenges. The students choose their topic, identify it, explain why they choose it and solve the problem. Thevathayan (2018) presented an experience evolving a hybrid-teaching model by using the action research cycle plan-act-observe-reflect over three semesters. The main novelty of the approach was the use of projects with varying levels, which gave students an enjoyable and beneficial project experience. Marques (2018) proposed a formative monitoring method to help students be aware of their individual and team performance. The results indicated that PBL effectively enhanced the learning experience in the instructional scenario studied. Schneider (2020) used PBL to enhance student engagement, and Daun (2016) discussed results from the long-term application of such a course design in a graduate setting. In addition, he indicated that project-based learning techniques foster different teaching goals in graduate and undergraduate settings. Du et al. (2013) developed a framework of change in educational culture by using a PBL methodology. This framework aims to inspire curriculum design for education and analyze the implementation of PBL in each cultural context.

Palmer and W. Hall (2011) presented PBL offering in engineering PBL at Griffith University in Australia. The author observed that students generally enjoyed the experience, and the aspects needing improvement were listed and documented. García-Martín and E.Pérez (2017) presented a method to guide teachers using PBL principles and several instructional design models. In particular, the process deals with the definition of a problem facing three fundamental issues in active learning, especially in PBL: Students' Motivation, Supporting Students' Work, and Autonomous Working. The authors focused on academic contexts where instructors are starting to use this Methodology and students are not dealing with ill-structured projects. Du Bani et al. (2018) presented the main challenges facing PBL. The challenges included the type of projects, how to team up students, how to proceed with planning, how to swap planning outputs among teams, and how to implement a Project.

2.2 Challenges and Risk Assessment of PBL Failure

Previous significant studies about the Challenges of PBL are presented herein. The Henderson et al. (2012) survey mentioned that faculty are aware of student-centered teaching methods but find it challenging to deal with unexpected issues during the implementation phase. Thus, they often return to traditional teaching methods. Kjellberg et al. (2015) stated that implementing PBL is the holistic perspective of the project and that in most projects, the non-technical responsibilities are not clearly defined. The author says the complete infrastructure is not defined, probably due to a holistic project perspective and project management methods.

These authors also stated that novice teams affected knowledge transfer and communication within extended teams, affecting group dynamics, commitment, and responsibilities. The authors highlighted that lack of teacher teams leads to one teacher acting as both examiner and PM. The authors also emphasized that the "two-hats" issue added to the teacher workload and created emotional stress due to the lack of tools and support and the constant brooding on addressing issues that appear. Beddoes et al. (2010) explained that challenges to the implementation and execution of PBL are both theoretical and practical. Theoretically, debates remain over the best approach to incorporate PBL and the performance necessary to benefit students. Some engineering educators argue that the maximum benefits of PBL will not be obtained unless it is implemented across the entire curriculum and all at once (Inelmen, 2003).

On the other hand, some argue that due to the significant differences between PBL and traditional methods, instructors should start with small-scale initiatives to incrementally familiarize themselves with PBL (Hansen, Cavers, & George, 2003). The changing roles of the teacher and the student are widely recognized as two of the most significant barriers to the implementation of PBL (Prince & Felder, 2006; Strobel, 2009). PBL can be difficult for faculty and students "because it challenges them to see learning and knowledge in new ways" and blurs boundaries (Savin-Baden, 2007, p. 24). For instance, students may be hostile to PBL because they are unaccustomed to the level of personal responsibility required and may experience conflicts with team members (Prince & Felder, 2006). Moreover, teachers often find it difficult to adjust to PBL (Prince & Felder, 2006; Thomas, 2000). Furthermore, institutional difficulties include resources, scalability, physical facilities, and management (Bielefeldt et al., 2009).

2.3 BBN (Bayesian Belief Network)

BBN has been widely used to estimate corrosion risks (Yang et al., 2016). Bayesian Network Networks were used to ease knowledge acquisition of causal dependence in CREAM (Ashrafi et al., 2016). The Bayesian variable was used in the selection to analyze regular resolution IV two-level fractional factorial designs (Chipman et al., 2016). BBN's is a causal structure used by probability risk analysis specialists to obtain information about important risk events and the necessary interventions to address risks (Rechenthin, 2004; Mosleh, 1992). The Use of BBN's in safety, maintenance, and reliability has increased quickly (Mahadevan, 2001). Bayesian methods have been used comprehensively in many applications and provide a structure for addressing the limitations of human reliability analysis (Podofilini and Dang, 2013; Mosleh and Apostolakis, 1986; Droguett et al., 2004; Groth and Swiler, 2013). None of the above previous studies deals with the application of BBN to the Risk Assessment of Project-Based Learning Failure. The objective of the BBN methodology is to allow more straightforward predictions of risk events and also execution of sensitivity analysis; it is a structure representing arguments when uncertainty exists.

2.4 AHP (Analytical Hierarchy Process)

Saaty (1980) was the first to use AHP as a decision-making tool to provide the relative weight of criteria based on a hierarchy structure. The author proposed the use of pairwise comparison to evaluate alternatives. The method has been used extensively to solve complex decision problems. It divides a problematic issue into smaller parts aiming at ranking them hierarchically. Thus, the relative importance of alternatives is weighed accordingly. In this paper, AHP is utilized to consider/prioritize the key risks affecting the PBL result. The AHP is an excellent tool to provide weight for the different risk levels; the first phase is to create a pairwise evaluation matrix (A), as introduced by (Saaty 1980), by utilizing the relative importance scale. The matrix A represents a pairwise evaluation matrix where each element "a_{ij}" (i, j = 1, 2, ..., n) represents the proportional importance of two compared elements (i and j). The higher the value, the stronger the first element preference(i) over the second (j). (MIs and Otcenaskova, 2013).

3 Methodology

The research was conducted in Google Scholar, Scielo, Scopus, and Web of Knowledge using the keywords: Active Learning; Engineering Education; PBL; Risk Assessment, BBN, and AHP. The following Journals related to engineering education listed in JCR Journal Citation Reports Full Journal List were also reviewed for state-of-the-art papers on the subject: 1 – International journal of engineering education – Ireland; 2 - Journal of

engineering education – USA; 3 - Journal of professional issues in engineering education and practice – USA; 4 - Computer applications in engineering education – USA; 5 - International journal of electrical engineering education – England; 6 - European journal of engineering education. For selecting the publications of interest, they were searched by title, abstract, and keywords, and the focus was on the papers published in the last five years. The following keywords were used: Active Learning; Engineering Education; PBL; Risk Assessment, BBN, AHP. The searched papers were reviewed by reading the abstract and introduction; those relevant to the research objectives were selected. In this project, 50 research papers were selected among 120 to identify risk factors in the PBL use and implementation. The papers covering problem-based learning and not covering the Design of PBL and challenges/risk assessment of PBL failure were disregarded.

A survey was conducted as a case study. The study adopted the approach of building theory from Case Study Research (Eisenhardt, 1898) and Kin (1999). It combined data from archives, interviews, and observations and focused on the application of PBL by a university in partnership with a company. A PBL process map was constructed, and a list of risk factors found in the researched literature and in the process map was then prepared. A quality management and planning tool named Relationship Digraph was used to cluster the risk factors into categories and establish the cause-and-effect relationship to the failure of PBL. A survey in Google forms was created to obtain the probability of students, professors, and organization leaders' risk factors. Students, professors, and professionals from a local university and its major partner company completed the survey in 2022. It was responded to by approximately 12 participants, who were asked to estimate the probability that a given risk could cause the failure of a PBL project. AHP (Analytical Hierarchy Process) was used to find the relative importance (impact) level of the risk categories. The global risk scores (combination of probability and impact scores) were obtained by multiplying the probabilities and impact scores. The next step was implementing risk responses to address the risk categories (Risk Priority Number). The last step was preparing the BBN and performing sensitivity analysis to identify the risks with a higher impact on the PBL failure. The steps of the Methodology are shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Methodology flowchart

4 Results

This section shows the process map, the list of risk factors impacting PBL failure, the AHP for the Technical Learning principle, the list of probability and impact scores, the BBN combining all risk factors, and the tornado chart resulting from sensitivity analysis. Following the sequence defined in the Methodology, the process map and relationship digraph was used to prepare the list of risk factors organized by risk categories. An AHP matrix was prepared for each Learning principle to obtain the risk factor's impact values. The probability values for risk factors were obtained with the survey. The probability and the impact values for each risk factor were combined to obtain the risk index. The risk index was color-coded as per the risk index value. Finally, a BBN was also used to identify the most significant risks impacting PBL projects using sensitivity analysis.

The flowchart in Figure 2. shows the process map used by universities in conjunction with partner companies in PBL projects and the risks presented in each step. The letters in red represent the category of risks: C: Cognitive Learning Failure, S: Social Learning Failure, and T: Theory and Practice Learning.

Figure 2. Structure in the conduction of PBL projects and risks.

The risk factors were clustered into categories to establish the cause-and-effect relationship to the failure of PBL. The affinity diagram was used to organize the risk factors within three learning principles and nine categories, as Xiangyun (2013) suggested. Risk factors leading to each risk category were identified based on the researched literature, as shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Risk Factors impacting PBL failure.

Type	Categories	Risks Identification	Risk Factors
C: Cognitive Learning Failure	CA: No Standardization of PBL Procedure	C1	Lack of procedure for PBL process
		C2	Students and professors not appropriately trained on the PBL procedure
		C3	Lack of standard work for the execution of PBL's
	CB: PBL specific requirements not defined accurately	C4	Poor explanation of expectations to students
		C5	Lack of background definition on principle behind projects
		C6	No clear definition of requirements
		C7	Project complexity incompatible with time and resources
	CC: Wrong Choice of Project	C8	The project is not related to discipline
		C9	Workload too heavy for the student
		C10	The low ability of students (slow learners)
S: Social Learning Failure	SA: Team Building practices not used	S1	Number of Students in project inadequate (too big or too small)
		S2	Project team members not equally strong
		S3	Assign students to teams rather than let them select the team themselves
	SB: PBL Professor not active in the project	S4	Professor does not give feedback on the project
		S5	Nonexistence of guidelines for team operation in the project
		S6	Students not encouraged by professors
	SC: Team lack of Motivation	S7	Some of the students not active in the project
		S8	No focus on the project
		S9	Relationship professor and student not good
		S10	Students and Professor lack patience and enthusiasm
T: Theory and Practice Learning Failure	TA: PBL Professor not prepared for the project	T1	Professor does not support knowledge base construction.
		T2	Professor does not support Argument base construction.
		T3	Lack of professor technical content knowledge and experience
		T4	Professor has no industrial skills.
	TB: No definition of PBL records organization	T5	Lack of definition for the project content organization
		T6	No definition of project report content
		T7	Problem-solving methods not defined
	TC: Students not prepared for the PBL	T8	Students are not familiar with the specific process theory behind PBL.
		T9	Students have no knowledge of Quality Tools for problem-solving
		T10	Students not trained on specific PBL process

The probabilities for each risk factor were elicited from students and professors using a Google Form survey. AHP was utilized to compare the risk factors in each learning principle category pairwise. An interview process was conducted to obtain from professors and students the degree of impact of each risk on the failure of PBL. The risk weight values (impact) were quantitatively calculated based on the completed pairwise comparative matrix. The empirical data was converted into mathematical models using a hierarchy table established by Saaty (2009). The relative importance of the risks is translated into the numerical pairwise comparison matrix shown in Table 2.

Table 2. Hierarchy table

Importance	Definition
1	Both elements are of equal importance
3	Moderate importance of one element compared to the other
5	Strong importance of one element compared to the other
7	Very strong importance of one element compared to the other
9	The extreme importance of one element over the other

AHP was utilized to obtain the impact for each risk and respective risk category. A pairwise comparative matrix was prepared, as shown in Table 3, for the Technical Learning principle, and similar tables were prepared for the other principles. An interview process was conducted to obtain from 3 professors and 6 students the degree of impact of each risk on the failure of PBL.

Table 3. AHP for the Technical Learning principle

Criteria Comparison Matrix										
<i>Risk Factors</i>	CA: No Standardization of PBL Procedure	CB: PBL specific requirements not defined	CC: Wrong Choice of Project	SA: Team Building practices not used	SB: PBL Professor not active in the project	SC: Team lack of Motivation	TA: PBL Professor not prepared for the project	TB: No definition of PBL records organization	TC: Students not prepared for the PBL	Weights
CA: No Standardization of PBL Procedure	1	1	7	5	3	7	3	5	3	0,26
CB: PBL specific requirements not defined accurately	1	1	3	5	3	7	3	7	3	0,23
CC: Wrong Choice of Project	1/7	1/3	1	1	5	3	3	3	3	0,13
SA: Team Building practices not used	1/5	1/5	1	1	1	1	1/3	3	3	0,07
SB: PBL Professor not active in the project	1/3	1/3	1/5	1	1	3	1	3	3	0,08
SC: Team lack of Motivation	1/7	1/7	1/3	1	1/3	1	1	3	1/3	0,04
TA: PBL Professor not prepared for the project	1/3	1/3	1/3	3	1	1	1	5	3	0,10
TB: No definition of PBL records organization	1/5	1/7	1/3	1/3	1/3	1/3	1/5	1	1/3	0,03
TC: Students not prepared for the PBL	1/3	1/3	1/3	1/3	1/3	3	1/3	3	1	0,06
TOTAL	3,69	3,82	13,53	17,67	15,00	26,33	12,87	33,00	19,67	

The impact scores shown in Table 3 were color-coded using Table 4.

Table 4. AHP

Impact Level Score		
Score	Impact Level	Impact
5	High	More than 0,16
4	Elevated	0,12-0,16
3	Moderated	0,08-0,11
2	Low	0,04-0,07
1	Limited	Less than 0,04

The final risk index for each risk factor was obtained in the following way. As an example, considering Table 6 (applicable to Theory and Practice Learning Failure), the probability for T1 is 0.7, and the impact is 0.05; based on Table 5, the probability rating score is (value: 4). The impact rating score is (value: 2) for the risk factor T1. Figure 2 is referenced to obtain the final risk index for T1. In this case, the final score is (value: 8), the product of 4 by 2. The risk index for the other Principles is calculated similarly.

Table 5. Probability and Impact Score.

Probability Level Score			Impact Level Score		
Score	Probability Level	Probability	Score	Impact Level	Impact
5	Expected	More than 0,80	5	High	More than 0,16
4	Very probable	0,51-0,80	4	Elevated	0,12-0,16
3	Probable	0,31-0,50	3	Moderated	0,08-0,11
2	Improbable	0,11-0,30	2	Low	0,04-0,07
1	Almost no probability	Less than 0,10	1	Limited	Less than 0,04

The global risk score (index) was determined using the risk scoring matrix shown in Figure 2 (Hyun et al., 2015). The final risk index is obtained by combining the probability and impact.

		RISK						
		Limited	Low	Moderate	Elevated	High		
		1	2	3	4	5		
Probability	Almost no probability	1	1	2	3	4	5	
	Unlikely	2	2	4	6	8	10	
	Probable	3	3	6	9	12	15	
	Very probable	4	4	8	12	16	20	
	Expected	5	5	10	15	20	25	
Risk Factor Classification								
1-5		Insignificant	6-9	Tolerable	10-16	Undesireble	17-25	Intolerable

Figure 2. Final Risk Index

The global risk score (index) for Cognitive Learning Failure, Social Learning Failure was determined using the same process.

Table 6. Probability and Impact Score Theory and Practice Learning Failure

Factors	Probability	Impact	Probability Score	Impact Score	Risk Index
T1 - Professor do not support knowledge base construction	0,7	0,05	4	2	8
T2 - Professor do not support Argument base construction	0,7	0,0404	4	2	8
T3 - Lack of professor technical content knowledge and experience	0,5	0,2401	3	5	15
T4 - Professor has no industrial skills	0,6	0,2189	4	5	20
T5 - Lack of definition for the project content organization	0,7	0,0457	4	2	8
T6 - No definition of report content	0,8	0,026	5	1	5
T7 - Problem solving methods not defined	0,6	0,1075	4	3	12
T8 - Students are not familiar with specific process theory behind PBL	0,2	0,0935	2	3	6
T9 - Students have no knowledge of Quality Tools for problem solving	0,5	0,1102	3	3	9
T10 - Students not trained on specific PBL industrial process	0,3	0,0666	2	2	4

The authors weighted the probability values obtained with the survey based on the respondents' experience, as shown in Table 7. The probabilities were then loaded into BBN software, and the probabilities of each risk were combined, allowing sensitivity analysis to define the most significant risk factor.

Table 7. Experience Period (E) & Weight

Experience Period (E) & Weight	
Less than 5 years	0.60
6-10 years	0.75
11-15 years	0.09
More than 15 years	1.00

The probabilities were loaded into BBN software. BBN was used because the statistical causal structure was key to obtaining information about risk events to mitigate them. Charts in Figures 3 and 4 could be generated using the software.

Figure 3. BBN combines all risk factors in the software

Figure 4. Tornado Chart

The Tornado chart originated from BBN (Figure 4) shows that the risks with the highest probabilities are shows that the highest risk Index is C4 (Poor explanation of expectations to students), C5 (Lack of background definition on principles behind projects), and C6 (No clear definition of requirements). The actions to be taken for risk factor C4 are ensuring the procedure clarifies expectations to the Professor and students. The procedure needs to be detailed enough to ensure repeatability and reproducibility. The action for risk factor C5 is to ensure the procedure also covers the principles behind the projects. The detailed explanation of the objectives and targets of each project is crucial to keep everybody in the same page. The action for risk factor C6 is to ensure the procedure covers the definition of project requirements. If the project requirements are not defined, it is difficult to monitor and control the performance.

5 Discussion of Results and Conclusion

As proposed in the introduction, the study demonstrated that AHP in conjunction with BBN could be used to assess and prioritize the risk factors of PBL failure in future studies. An in-depth analysis of current literature about the subject allowed the identification of risk factors in this process. The preparation of a global risk matrix is proposed since it provides critical information considering identifying and prioritizing the potential risks that could cause PBL failure. It is an effective decision-making process for universities. This study shows evidence that PBL, in general, is subjected to a great variety of risks, some of them capable of compromising the teaching quality in the universities. Probabilistic risk analysis plays a significant role in understanding and implementing risk responses to avoid failure. An in-depth search for previous work dealing with risks in PBL was conducted and is described herein, and a model is proposed for risk assessment. This study is significant because understanding the significant risks in the PBL process can influence the decision of professors and university engineering school coordinators. Applying this innovative risk assessment method in the PBL process fills a gap in the literature since no previous work dealt with this specific subject. The contribution is significant since risk assessment in the PBL process permits decision-makers to assign funds for critical activities that can impact universities' teaching quality. As initially proposed, a model for risk assessment of PBL failure is being proposed that allows the combined application of AHP and Bayesian Networks to prioritize risks. The proposed application sought to analyze and define the primary risk factors and critical events that could lead to a failure in PBL.

In response to the first question, "1 - What are the most significant risk factors for using PBL in collaboration with local companies when teaching engineering students?" The most significant risks were identified. The Tornado chart originated from BBN (Figure 4) shows that the risks with the highest risk Index is C4 (Poor explanation of expectations to students), C5 (Lack of background definition on principles behind projects), and C6 (No clear definition of requirements). The result of AHP for the Cognitive Learning principle shows that the most impactful risk factors are C1 (Lack of procedure for the PBL process) and C3 (Lack of standard work for the execution of PBLs). The AHP for the Social Learning principle shows that the most impactful risk factors are S3 (Assign students to teams rather than let them select the team themselves) and S6 (Students not encouraged by professors). The AHP for the Technical Learning principle shows that the most impactful risk factors are T3 (Lack of professor technical content knowledge and experience) and T4 (lack of industrial skills). The AHP for risk factors categories shows that the most impactful risk factors are CA (No Standardization of PBL Procedure) and CB PBL specific requirements not defined accurately).

In response to the second question, " What are the probability and the impact of these risks and the global risk scores? " The probability and impact (global risk scores) for all the risks are provided. The Probability and Impact Score for Cognitive Learning Failure shows that the highest risk Index is C1 (Lack of procedure for PBL process), and C2 Students and professors are not appropriately trained on the PBL procedure). The Probability and Impact Score for the Social Learning Failure shows that the highest risk Index is S3 (Assign students to teams rather than let them select the team themselves), S6 (Students not encouraged by professors), and S9 (Relationship professor and student not good). The Probability and Impact Score Theory and Practice Learning Failure shows that the highest risk Index is T4 (Professor has no industrial skills) and T3 (Lack of professor technical content knowledge and experience).

In response to the third question, "3 What are the responses to high Index risks, and how to combine the risks and conduct a sensitivity analysis with BBN" The responses to high index risks are the following: The actions to be taken for risk factor C1 are the issue of a procedure to document the PBL process. Risk factor C2 is to train professors on the documented procedure. The actions to be taken for risk factor S3 are not assigning the students to the PBL group but letting the student choose the group he wants to work with and the action for the risk factor. S6 trains professors to encourage students to work on the PBL, and S9 provides training on team building to professors and students. The actions to be taken for risk factor T3 are ensuring the Professor assigned to a project has the required technical knowledge and experience. The action to risk factor T4 is to ensure the Professor has practical experience in the industry where the PBL project will be developed. A sensitivity analysis with BBN. The Tornado chart shows that the risks with the highest probabilities are shows that the highest risk Index is C4 (Poor explanation of expectations to students), C5 (Lack of background definition on principles behind projects), and C6 (No clear definition of requirements). The actions to be taken for risk factor C4 are ensuring the procedure clarifies expectations to the Professor and students. The action for risk factor C5 is to ensure the procedure also covers the principles behind the projects. The action for risk factor C6 is to make sure the procedure covers the definition of project requirements.

The target of the study was to identify the critical risk factors that could affect PBL and propose an optimized process that has quality in PBLs. The implications are relevant since changes in the PBL process can improve the result substantially. By following the revised process, PBL failures can be prevented. The proposed Methodology revealed some critical results, thus contributing to previous studies on the subject and may help overcome some of the challenges of professors, students, and other professionals looking for quality education. The study was conducted based on the experience and knowledge of professors and students. It is believed that the present study will augment the knowledge of professors, engineering students, and engineering school coordinators and help in the application process. As explained in the Introduction Section, several papers have been published addressing PBL use in different domains in the latest years. However, no previous study could be found covering the application of AHP and BBN to identify risks of the application of PBL. It is noteworthy that this paper proposes an optimized approach that could be used in any university or teaching organization.

This proposed process can guide the universities under the traditional teaching process to achieve quality improvement by following the proposed Methodology. That helps to impact results, representing considerable teaching gains significantly. The proposed method, enhanced by improved communication, enables any university to increase efficiency in education. This study shows evidence that the quality of the PBL process is affected by several factors, some of which can compromise the reliability of the teaching institution. In this regard, process analysis played a crucial role in understanding and implementing actions to improve it.

This study is significant because understanding the most impactful risk factors in the conduction of PBL can influence professors, students, and decision-makers in universities. As evidenced by the results, the modified method can help to optimize engineering teaching. As expected, the contribution is significant; it is believed that the present study will augment the knowledge of professors and students concerning the use of the PBL process to improve the quality and effectiveness of the teaching. Scope for future research: This study opened some new research avenues for the future. Opportunities for other case studies are abundant. They could be related to a broader application of risk analysis of PBL in specific cases, enhancing the current Methodology in use and reducing the risk of failures.

6 References

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